

CONDITIONS FOR THE OCCURRENCE OF CONFLICTS IN LABOR TEAMS AND METHODS OF CONFLICT ANALYSIS

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Abstract. *This article explains the conditions and methods of conflict analysis in labor unions, and the fact that finding a solution to a conflict is a complex, long-term process that requires patience and satisfaction and requires the parties to work on it for a long time.*

Keywords: *work, team, conflict, conditions, analysis, method, conflict resolution, complex, long-term, patience and satisfaction, vertical and horizontal, antagonistic, compromise, open, hidden, potential, reasonable, personal, interpersonal, intergroup, national, ethnic, transnational, production, emotional-emotional, "animal" methods.*

Conflicts are one of the most urgent social problems of our time. Why do various conflicts arise in labor unions? There are several reasons for this:

- 1) according to the direction of influence: vertical and horizontal;
- 2) according to the method of conflict resolution: antagonistic and conflict leading to agreement - compromise;
- 3) according to the level of manifestation: open, hidden, potential, reasonable;
- 4) according to the number of participants: personal, interpersonal, group;
- 5) according to the nature of origin: national, ethnic, inter-ethnic, production, emotional-emotional.

There are two different conditions for conflicts to arise. Objective conditions:

- poor working conditions;
- improper distribution of duties and responsibilities among employees;
- imbalances in the management system;
- non-observance of professionalism appropriate to assigned tasks;
- unfair distribution of work due to lack of jobs;
- observation of cases of injustice in the organization of labor and payment of wages.

Subjective conditions in the occurrence of conflicts:

- appearance of negative ways in business relations;
- manifestation of personal characteristics in interpersonal relations;
- observation of inaccuracy and illiteracy in the organization of transactions.

Each conflict is analyzed as a separate event, but there are certain laws common to all of them, which include, first of all, its stages or phases:

- I. Pre-conflict stage - confrontation.
- II. The conflict itself is a compromise or a fight.
- III. Conflict resolution - communication or dissonance.

Five main ways of behaving in a conflict situation can be distinguished:

- 1) flexibility, flexibility;

- 2) take oneself aside (left);
- 3) opposition (conflict);
- 4) cooperation;
- 5) compromise

1. Adaptability, compromise - individual actions are aimed at maintaining or restoring positive relations with the opponent at the expense of their own interests. This approach can be used in cases where the individual's share is not so large or the reason for the disagreement is more important for the individual than for his opponent. Such behavior is used in situations where the situation is not so important, it is more important to maintain good relations with the opponent than to protect one's own interests, and the individual's chances of victory and the strength in his hands are low.

2. To withdraw oneself (leave, run away). Such a moral individual is chosen in cases where he does not want to protect his rights, cooperate in the development of a decision, refuses to express his position, and avoids the debate. This method avoids responsibility for decisions when the end of the conflict is not important for the individual, or the situation is very complicated and the resolution of the conflict requires a lot of effort from the participants, or if not, his power to resolve the conflict in his favor, can be used in cases where the authority is not present.

3. Opposition, competition. An individual's active struggle for his own interests is characterized by the use of all available means to achieve the set goals: power, coercion, other means of putting pressure on opponents, using the dependence of other participants on him. . The situation is considered by the individual as a matter of victory or defeat, which implies a firm position towards opponents and uncompromising antagonism towards the opposing participants of the conflict.

4. Cooperation. It means that the individual actively participates in the search for a solution that satisfies all the participants involved in the interaction, but does not forget his own interests. An open exchange of ideas, the interest of all participants in the conflict in developing a common solution is assumed. This form requires positive work and participation from all parties. In such an approach, there is a possibility that the issue or the disagreements that have arisen will be thoroughly discussed and a common solution will be developed, respecting the interests of all participants.

5. Compromise. It occupies a special intermediate position and includes both active and passive forms of influence. It partially resolves conflicting interactions, and despite the fact that many compromises have been made, the causes have not been completely eliminated. This behavior means that opponents have equal power, power, and mutually exclusive interests, and that they have limited time to search for a better solution, until an intermediate solution will satisfy them until a certain time. will be

In some cases, confrontation can be more effective than adaptation, compromise, or even compromise in terms of resolving conflict in reasonable, controllable terms. In this case, it is important that the defeat does not cause the expansion of the base for forming new conflicts and the area of conflict actions.

In our previous articles, we have gained some knowledge about the content of conflicts, their causes, and what situations arise in the conflict. We realized that the most necessary condition is that the conflict should not be left alone. We have seen that active intervention in the conflict, managing it and working out its solution in cooperation leads to finding a solution to the conflict. We talked about

human qualities and skills necessary for conflict resolution. But at the same time, in order to find a solution to the conflict, it is necessary to master the unique methods of conflict management. Knowing and applying information about conflict management can also bring peace into your life. In conflictology, conflict management methods are developed based on people's character, behavior, and psychology.

Now let's look at how to manage conflicts. There are five main ways to manage conflict. Usually, in conflict theory, these methods are given in relation to the behavioral characteristics of some "animal" based on the behavior of various animals. We will consider the "animal" methods of conflict management developed by us and widely used in the theory of conflictology.

Your task is to find out which method is more correct and suitable for your character from the highlighted methods. But there are different situations in life, and it is not correct to study the complex character of a person by only one method. In many cases, it is necessary to assume that the human character is not directly analogous to only one method, but sometimes to a mixture of methods. Also, a person's behavior in one or another conflict situation depends on that situation in its own way. So, conflictology has the following methods of conflict management.

Adaptation and habituation method - "SHEEP";

"Whatever you say, I agree with you."

A person with the method of adaptation and adaptation always tries to adapt himself to some reality. Even in emergency situations, he goes by the way of agreement with the situation and the people who caused the situation. You always try to show your approval to the other person, because this way creates an opportunity to avoid conflict, not to openly resist, to withdraw from it, not to actively participate in the conflict. You are afraid of the conflict situation itself. A conflict situation for you is a disruption of a peaceful and peaceful life, new decisions are made, something is demanded of you. Therefore, you are afraid to actually make decisions and try to get yourself out of this situation. That's why you are often judged. You don't resist them, because you don't like conflict. "You're right, it was stupid to plant your apple tree in my yard, because my children will enjoy its fruits." Death is better for you than angering someone. You are worried about other people's opinion about you, their anger and rage. That's why you don't show anyone what you're really thinking and what feelings are bothering you. The most important thing for you is a warm relationship, even if it's fake, greetings and that's it. So everything is fine. It is very important for you to have a warm relationship with those around you, and you will tolerate them even if they harm you and treat you unfairly. With this, you will prevent conflicts in your life by being resistant to oppression and injustice. You manage conflicts by being inactive and swimming in the direction of flowing water, you do not even think about the essence of the conflict, but you overcome the conflict without actively interfering, taking the emotional burden on yourself.

Advantages of the method. As an Aries, you regularly maintain peaceful and friendly relationships with others. Because your burden does not fall on anyone. Everyone uses you. You endure everything. You will be more attentive to others, so others will feel the need for you. They openly talk about their pains and relationships in front of you. Because there is no harm from you.

Disadvantages of the method. Your demands, your feelings are very little considered, your needs are not taken into account and very little is fulfilled. If injustices against you increase in this situation, hidden anger and hatred will grow in your heart, but if you are surrounded by people who appreciate this quality of yours, your life will be as peaceful and peaceful as you want. But you always feel that you are weak.

Method "It's not my business" - "STRAUS";

"Leave me alone!" I don't care about anything!"

You avoid the conflict instead of looking for a solution, but this avoidance is different from the "let it go" method. If the put method recognizes that there is a conflict, you assert that there is no conflict. That is, you will not recognize the conflict at all, as a result of which your emotions will not suffer. You hide from it somewhere, you don't want to admit that there is a problem. You do not think that a conflict has arisen and that it should be resolved. You will avoid problems. "If they are not thought of, they will disappear," you think. When "Koy" is defeated, you will not even recognize its existence. You can't force yourself to think about the solution to the conflict, you don't even want to share it. If you find yourself in a conflict situation, your first reaction is to say, "It's none of my business." It's more comfortable for you to see yourself as someone who knows nothing, sees nothing, and can't solve anything. You run away from the place where the conflict arose, go out to another room or go to the samovar, try to change the topic of the conversation, postpone the search for a solution to the conflict or consider it "not available at all". This idea of yours becomes such a fixed idea that you start to treat others as if nothing happened at all, don't bother me. Therefore, if others look for a solution to the conflict and begin to solve it, the most favorable situation for you will arise. The most important thing is that they don't bother you. Let them solve everything without you. You usually prefer to have other people solve your problems.

Advantages of the method. You will never get into a situation of squabbling, fighting, fighting. Because you always manage to avoid any conflict. Keeping yourself out of dangerous situations and being able to get out unscathed is a very good skill. You will never face physical violence based on conflicts, you will be considered the guardian of your own health.

Disadvantages of the method. You do not consider yourself to be strong and able to defend yourself. Like a straus, you stick your head in the ground whenever you see a conflict. You will never be ready to solve your problems, you will not look for a way to solve them. And even if your problems are solved by others, you do not interfere with them, even if you understand that this solution may be superficial, unfair and temporary, that is, temporary, transient. And it can be solutions and conclusions against your interests. In general, you don't hate problems, you are afraid of them, so the worst result of this method is that you turn to other harmful ways to get rid of your problems, so there is a possibility that you will turn to drugs and alcohol.

Aggressive method - "SHARK" "Who says what?!"

"Who is against me?! Is he cool?!"

Your poet is to always be the "winner" in any situation. In a conflict situation, winning for you is better than the solution of the problem, that is, the solution of the conflict. You want to "win" even if you know it's your fault. You will stop at nothing to be a "winner". You prefer to be a "winner" more than conflict resolution, problem solving, and you plan and act accordingly. In fact, you don't know or believe that conflict resolution is the "right" way. You are ready to blame anyone else and often use words like "must", "must", "must", "must". You are quick-tempered and quick-tempered, you have a strong temper, it is common for you to be rude, and you are not able to listen to someone patiently. You perceive listening to your opponent's thoughts in silence as submission to him. You want people around you to see that you will definitely "win" in any situation and to recognize your strength. You don't think about the violation of justice. You get

very hot, you put pressure on others, you can even shout. In fact, in many cases, you will win, and this will happen at the expense of suffering and harming the interests of others.

Advantages of the method. You are always open about your feelings and can express your thoughts freely. You like to be active, take responsibility and take risks. Always having the opportunity to vent negative emotions will protect you from emotional crises. You are not crushed and suffering inside. The word depression is yours.

Disadvantages of the method. The fact that you act only for your own interests does not leave out friends and loyal people around you, many of your loved ones suffer from your emotional outbursts, your disregard for the opinions of others, and the fact that you only believe in yourself will make your relationships with people difficult. You rarely listen to the advice of others and work in agreement with others. More people will have to agree with you. The problem is that it's very easy for your personality to turn violent. You don't hesitate to commit violence and carry it out. You take violence for granted. An increase in violence can lead to crime. But you don't think about it. The fact that you always win becomes a necessity, a commonplace. You don't think that your "win" is someone else's "loss".

Compromise method - "FOX"

"I am ready for anything for you.

Can I be of any use to you?!"

You know that every conflict has its own solution. But you don't want to spend a lot of time and effort on conflict resolution. Therefore, you are looking for the lightest and fastest solution. For this, you try to flatter, praise, sacrifice your life, hypocrisy, please others. Your motto is "first one step back, then two steps forward". "Are you so angry? "Okay, let it go, I'll do it myself." "Yes, I'm guilty, let me try again. I understand everything you said. I will do as you ordered...". "Whatever you say, there is no one sharper than you in this world, if a snake moves on the ground, you know...". You don't feel ashamed to compromise, but you put yourself above those who couldn't compromise. Because you consider the inability to compromise as a flaw in human nature, it is your fault. You try to agree in any situation, compromise is your vital need. In this case, neither side loses, but neither side wins. You often look for a favorable situation to realize your goals and wait for this favorable situation. You are a small "small" person and you fully believe that you can do "big" things, and you can do it. You masterfully use compromises to appear submissive and then dominate.

Advantages of the method. Your behavior is flexible and you feel at ease in any situation and situation. You believe in yourself. You can always withdraw if required. You know that retreating when necessary is to preserve one's interests. You do not hesitate to retreat, this is your achievement. Therefore, you can quickly come to conclusions with another person that are satisfactory and beneficial for both of you. There is an opportunity to take advantage of you in negotiations. Your ability to agree and compromise can bring a solution to a conflict situation, even for a short time. A person who can compromise inspires trust in many people. Trust is one of the necessary conditions for conflict resolution.

Disadvantages of the method. You are more interested in a quick solution than a fair solution. Therefore, your solution may be unfair and temporary. You are in a hurry, so you don't always have time to look for all the available ways to resolve the conflict. Conflict resolution is likely to be temporary when you intervene, and then develop all over again. Believing in your abilities, the main problem in the conflict may remain problematic.

Cooperation method - "BOYOGLI"

"I am always ready for cooperation!"

You are a person who is always ready to play the role of a partner in your character, knowledge and behavior. You are open to cooperation and now considered human. Therefore, in a conflict situation, all your attention is focused on finding a solution to the conflict. You do not condemn anyone, you do not blame anyone. You listen to what others have to say and take into account the feelings and needs of others. You can talk about your emotions and feelings calmly, calmly, without emotions. You can fully control your emotions. Your voice, facial expressions, speech, open heart, sincerity - everything is focused on finding a solution to the conflict. You offer different ideas and ways to resolve the conflict, you try to find a fair solution for both parties. It is important for you to take into account the interests of both parties, so that both of them can be "winners" and be satisfied. You will try to make a mutually beneficial judgment. In cooperation with others, you can develop several options for decisions that satisfy each of you.

If you feel that the conflict is out of your control and you cannot fully resolve it yourself, or if you realize that the conflict is turning violent, you are always ready to ask for help from others, that is, a third party. Your decision involves elements of compromise, compromise, and consent to dissent. You are able to bring conflicts to a complete solution.

Advantages of the method. Most of your decisions are usually fair and long lasting. Your relationships with others are built on trust. There will be many people, friends, brothers and sisters around you. Your friends trust you to share their feelings and secrets. You appreciate the dignity and personality of others and respect their hidden feelings. Everyone is ready to help you when you need it. In your character, the subtlety, observation, and judgment will be strong. Both adults and children obey your decisions. You can take responsibility for yourself and live as a guardian of justice.

Disadvantages of the method. Being an "owl" in real life is not easy. It places a great responsibility on a person. Others always have to walk with pain and sorrow. Therefore, no one considers it easy to be an "owl". Being an "owl" requires a person's internal culture, respect for dignity, knowledge and skills, time, responsibility, courage and self-confidence. Cultivating these qualities is not an easy task. At the same time, being able to use this ability is not easy.

Not everyone will like your being a guardian of justice, and there will be those who oppose you.

Thus, in conclusion, it should be noted that there are methods of conflict management, and each person uses a method related to his character. Knowing the methods of conflict management helps and helps a person to better understand himself and analyze his steps. Each method has advantages and disadvantages. Therefore, strengthening the advantages and cleaning one's behavior from the disadvantages makes it possible to avoid conflicts in conflict situations.

Conflict management methods require specific skills from a person, and in fact, conflict management is not an easy task. But a person who has learned to manage conflicts can always clear his life and the lives of those around him of problems and create alternative conditions for them to live correctly, justly and peacefully.

Therefore, finding a solution to the dispute is a complex, long-term process that requires patience and satisfaction, and requires the parties to work on it for a long time. Finding a solution to the conflict is a way for the parties to understand and understand each other.

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